

**DIFFERENCES IN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH
TO CHILDREN AND ADULTS****Hazratova Aziza Kuchkin kizi**

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the differences, similarities, stages, and challenges of learning a foreign language between young and old. It also discusses innovative methods of learning a foreign language today and tips on how to understand and learn complex terms

After our homeland gained independence, the demand for learning a foreign language in our country has been increasing, and the conditions for this are gradually being created. Nowadays, not only school, lyceum, college and institute students, but also preschoolers and employees working in various fields are learning a foreign language, especially English. Of course, there are certain reasons for this, namely, learning the languages of economically, scientifically and culturally developed countries, as well as a key factor in deeply mastering the achievements of world science and technology. Language learning also depends on age. Psychologists have published many guides on this. Psychologists believe that young children learn foreign languages and various scientific knowledge faster and easier than older children.

Young people have a strong tendency to learn, imitate, and have a strong interest in learning things. I think the main reason for this is that children have more time than adults. Young children are naturally more inclined to learn languages. That's why I believe it's important to teach them through easy and fun methods and games at first, rather than suddenly teaching them difficult grammar rules to help them learn a language. The following methods can be used to teach children English meaningfully and effectively and to memorize complex words:

- explaining the topic in an interesting way through songs, cartoons and poems in a foreign language;
- games related to mental and physical condition;
- role play, when the teacher teaches some information, the names of animals or birds, through role playing, the child repeats and imitates the sentences or words they use, and by imitating the sounds of animals, their memory increases and their interest increases.

In addition, thematic environments, i.e. the teacher's ability to create an environment based on the topic, make it easier for children to learn the language and they learn better. For example: in the birthday, in the shop, in the kitchen, in the garden, etc. It is also important for the teacher to provide riddles related to the lesson in English or Uzbek, depending on the level, in each lesson and to engage the children in the lesson. Because the children's curiosity, that is, their interest in learning new things, encourages them to find the answer to the riddle faster and more correctly and sharpens their brains. It should also be noted that when learning English, learners are divided into several groups based on age. That is, since children and older learners have different social, cognitive, and psychological characteristics in the language learning process, their language learning strategies and effective methods and benefits are also different.

Different methods have been used to teach older English learners. That is, older learners create vocabulary by learning more analytical and information comprehensive rules in language learning.

Examples of these approaches include:

- Goal-oriented exercises: Adults learn a language for travel, work, or academic purposes. Therefore, the exercises and homework assignments are tailored to that purpose.
- Learning and explaining grammar and rules: Adults try to learn a language faster and more thoroughly and create vocabulary by knowing the rules.

Of course, many people may wonder: Why hasn't the same method been developed for learning a foreign language for both adults and children? Could this be an effective method or is it wrong?

Of course, these questions are valid, but there are also underlying reasons for these differences. The first and most important reason is the psychological differences between ages. Young people remember language naturally, while adults often remember and learn through logical analysis and repeated repetition. We also encounter many differences between attention and concentration. Children can pay attention for a short time, while adults are resistant to long-term activities. Another difference is motivation. Young people learn more through encouragement and interest. If you constantly encourage and praise them for what they are learning and doing, their interest will increase and they will study harder. Older people, on the other hand, have a clear result and goal. This forces them to keep moving forward. Innovative language learning methods are also being developed for all language learners.

This, of course, is also related to modern technology. It would not be wrong to say that the above are today's innovative ideas.

In conclusion, language learning for young children should be taught not as a specific obligation, but based on the interests and desires of the children, and should be constantly encouraged. For older children, the most effective way to teach a language is through goal-oriented exercises, which help them to master grammatical knowledge in depth. When these approaches are combined, the learning process will be interesting and effective for both groups

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